

Loneliness and Locus of Control among Young Adults Belonging To Joint Families and Nuclear Families

Pooja Agrawal¹, Varsha Singh^{2*}, Abhijeet Chore³

¹ P.G. students, Department of Psychology, School of Allied Health Care and Sciences, Jain (Deemed-to-be University), Bangalore-560066, Karnataka., India.

^{2*} Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, School of Allied Health Care and Sciences, Jain (Deemed-to-be University), Bangalore-560066, Karnataka., India.

³ Professor, Department of Psychology, Dr. Viswanath Karad Maharashtra Institute of Technology, World Peace University, Pune- 411038 Maharashtra, India.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7870493>

Published Date: 27-April-2023

Abstract: Family plays an important and powerful role in the lives of young adults. Adulthood is a crucial age range for young people, as they face a variety of difficulties in their lives at this age. Young adults may face rejection and feelings of isolation. The aim of this research is to examine the degree of loneliness and the type of locus of control among young adults from joint and nuclear families. A total of 134 young adults between the ages of 18 and 22, from both joint and nuclear families, were recruited. For data collection, random sampling was used as a sampling technique. The UCLA Loneliness Scale (version 3) was created by Daniel W. Russell in 1996, and the participants were given the Locus of Control Scale Indian Adaptation of the Levenson Scale (Vohra, 1992). Since the research was conducted in 2019 during the COVID-19 Pandemic, data was collected online using Google Forms. Microsoft Office Excel was used to analyze the results. Two samples were used for summary statistics and the t-test, assuming unequal variance. The findings revealed that there was no difference in levels of loneliness between adults from joint families and those from nuclear families. It also observed that among young adults from joint families and nuclear families, there was no significant difference in internal locus of control and chance factor of locus of control.

Keywords: Loneliness, Locus of Control, Young adults, Joint families, Nuclear families.

I. INTRODUCTION

Family structure is conceptualized as the configuration of role, power and status, and relationship in the family. There are two types of family structures: traditional and nuclear. Traditional family is the one living jointly and consists of members from different generations. Nuclear family is the one, in which the group consists of a male, his wife and their children. (N Kaura, R Sharma, 2015)

All families are different, and the ups and downs of family life have a huge effect on children and young people.

A study done by Ditommaso et al. (2005), found out that there exists a meaningful relation between feeling of loneliness and, and culture and family. The study shows that in a culture which lays emphasis on family, an individual feels less lonely than in a culture where a family is not given emphasis.

Loneliness is a distressing experience that occurs when a person's social relationships are perceived by that person to be less in quantity, and especially in quality, than desired. (L Hawkey, 2015).

Locus of Control is a psychological concept that refers to how strongly people believe they have control over the situations and experiences that affect their lives. (Glossary of Education Reform, 2013) As a result, there are two types of locus of control: internal and external locus of control. External locus of control is characterized by the feeling that outcomes are more a function of circumstance, luck, chance, or the control of powerful others, or are unpredictable due to the complexity of circumstances, while internal locus of control is characterized by the feeling that events are dependent on one's own, whereas. External locus of control is defined by the feeling that outcomes are more a function of fate, circumstance, chance, or the control of powerful others, or are unpredictable due to the complexity of situations, while internal locus of control is characterized by the feeling that outcomes are more a result of fate, luck, chance, or the control of powerful others, or are unpredictable due to the complexity of situations. Studying locus of control is an important aspect of young adults, as it contributes to the formation of their personality. Factors such as age, socioeconomic status, family style, and cultural stability affect the formation of this locus, which is linked to family style and cultural stability. Different families with different environments affect the Locus of Control, making it an important factor of study.

This present study therefore investigates the role of type of family among young adults in regards to their level of loneliness and type of locus of control.

II. METHODOLOGY

Objectives

The study's objectives were formulated as follows:

1. To assess (a) Level of Loneliness (b) Internal and External Locus of Control (c) among Young Adults.
2. To assess the effect of nuclear family type on loneliness and locus of control among young adults.
3. To assess the effect of Joint family type on loneliness and locus of control among young adults.

III. HYPOTHESIS

H1) There will be a significant difference in the level of loneliness among young adults belonging to joint families and nuclear families.

H2) There will be a significant difference among young adults belonging to nuclear and joint families on the powerful factor of locus of control.

H3) Young Adults belonging to joint and nuclear families and joint families will differ significantly on the chance control factor of locus of control.

H4) Individual control factor of locus of control will differ significantly among young adults belonging to nuclear and joint families.

IV. SAMPLE

In the present study total number of sample includes 134 college going young adults (54 Joint Families and 80 Nuclear Families). The age of the young adults ranges from 18 to 22 years. Sample collection was done through online mode with the help of google forms as the research was conducted during the COVID-19 Pandemic. Random Sampling was used as a sampling technique for data collection.

V. MEASURING INSTRUMENTS

1. UCLA Loneliness Scale The UCLA Loneliness Scale (version 3)

This scale is developed by Daniel W. Russell in 1996. It is a 20-item scale designed to measure one's subjective feelings of loneliness as well as a feeling of isolation. The measure has high internal consistency (coefficient alpha=.96) and a test-retest correlation over a two-month period of 0.73. Concurrent and preliminary construct validity are indicated by correlations with self-reports of current loneliness and related emotional states, and by volunteering for a "loneliness clinic."

2. Locus of Control Scale Indian Adaptation of Levenson Scale (Vohra, 1992)

The locus of control scale contains 24 statements covering the areas like Powerful others (P), Individual control (I) and Chance control (C). The test retest reliability coefficient was found to be 0.76. The present scale was validated against the

Rotter's Locus of control scale that is the concurrent validity was established. Scores of both the scales were then correlated with each other and the correlation co-efficient was found to be 0.54.

VI. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data was put into statistical analysis after the study was completed. The data was analyzed with the help of Microsoft Excel. The raw data was first used to calculate the descriptive statistics and then the t-test assuming unequal variances was used for the comparison of the data.

VII. RESULTS

Table 1: Table showing Mean, Standard Deviation Scores for Young Adults in Joint and Nuclear Families on the Powerful Others, Chance Control and Individual Control Factor of Locus of Control and Loneliness.

Family Type	N	Variables							
		Powerful Other Locus of Control		Chance Control Locus of Control		Individual Control Locus of Control		Loneliness	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Nuclear Families	80	27.87	6.25	25.29	7.96	33.89	6.43	44.87	4.33
Joint Families	54	21.49	9.41	25.94	7.77	33.60	5.70	45.94	3.46

The tabular presentation of data shows the Mean and the Standard Deviation scores of young adults in nuclear and joint families on powerful others (27.87, 21.49), chance control (25.29, 25.94) and individual control (33.89, 33.60) factor of locus of control and also of loneliness (44.87, 45.94) respectively. It means that young adults belonging to nuclear families have a high "Powerful Others" factor of Locus of Control as compared to joint family's young adults. It also indicates that young adults from joint and nuclear families have a similar effect of chance control factor of locus of control in their life. It also indicates that there is a similar effect of internal locus of control in young adults belonging to joint and nuclear families also shows that young adults belonging to joint families have more loneliness than in nuclear families.

Table 2: Table showing the t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances scores of Young Adults Belonging to Joint and Nuclear Families on Loneliness Factor T-test: two samples assuming unequal variance of Loneliness

Loneliness	Nuclear Family	Joint Family
Mean	44.87341772	45.94339623
Variance	18.80428432	12.01596517
Observations	79	53
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	126	
t Stat	-1.569522617	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.059517069	
t Critical one-tail	1.657036982	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.119034138	
t Critical two-tail	1.978970602	

The table shows the result of the t-test: two samples assuming unequal variances which were calculated on the loneliness factor of young adults belonging to joint and nuclear families. The analysis between the two variables was not found to be significant as the t calculated value is -1.569522617 which is less than t critical one tail 1.657036982 and t critical two-tail 1.978970602. Results say that there is no significant relationship between loneliness among young adults belonging to joint families and nuclear families.

Table 3: Table showing the t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances scores of Young Adults Belonging to Joint and Nuclear Families on Individual Factor of Locus of Control

Individual Factor	Nuclear Family	Joint Family
Mean	33.89873418	33.60377358
Variance	41.34858812	32.51306241
Observations	79	53
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	

Df	120	
t Stat	0.276637899	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.391267041	
t Critical one-tail	1.657650899	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.782534081	
t Critical two-tail	1.979930405	

The table shows the result of the t-test: two samples assuming unequal variances which were calculated on the Individual Factor of Locus of Control of young adults belonging to joint and nuclear families. The analysis between the two variables was not found to be significant as the t calculated value is 0.276637899 which is less than t critical one tail 1.657650899 and the t critical two-tail 1.97.

Results say that there is no significant relationship between internal locus of control among young adults belonging to joint families and nuclear families.

Table 4: Table showing the t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances scores of Young Adults Belonging to Joint and Nuclear Families on Powerful Factor of Locus of Control

Powerful Factor of Locus of Control	Nuclear Family	Joint Family
Mean	27.87341772	21.49056604
Variance	39.11197663	88.60087083
Observations	79	53
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	83	
t Stat	4.336157549	
P(T<=t) one-tail	2.02495E-05	
t Critical one-tail	1.663420175	
P(T<=t) two-tail	4.04989E-05	
t Critical two-tail	1.98895978	

The table shows the result of t-test: two sample assuming unequal variances which was calculated on Powerful Factor of Locus of Control of young adults belonging to joint and nuclear families. The analysis between the two variables was not found to be significant as t calculated value is 4.336157549 which is more than t critical one tail 1.663420175 and t critical two-tail 1.98895978

Results says that there is a significant relationship between loneliness among young adults belonging to joint families and nuclear families.

Table 5: Table showing the t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Unequal Variances scores of Young Adults Belonging to Joint and Nuclear Families on the Chance Factor of Locus of Control

Chance Factor of Locus of Control	Nuclear Family	Joint Family
Mean	25.29113924	25.94339623
Variance	63.4654333	60.43904209
Observations	79	53
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	114	
t Stat	-0.467844983	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.320394307	
t Critical one-tail	1.658329969	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.640788614	
t Critical two-tail	1.980992298	

The table shows the result of the t-test: two samples assuming unequal variances which were calculated on the Chance Factor of Locus of Control of young adults belonging to joint and nuclear families. The analysis between the two variables was not found to be significant as t calculated value is -0.467844983 which is less than t critical one tail 1.658329969 and t critical two-tail 1.980992298.

Results say that there is no significant relationship between the Chance Factor of locus of control among young adults belonging to joint families and nuclear families.

VIII. DISCUSSION

The title of the present research is “loneliness and locus of control among young adults belonging to nuclear and joint families”. For this, a sample of 134 college-going young adults (80 nuclear families and 54 joint families) was taken. Tools used for the study were The UCLA Loneliness Scale (version 3) is developed by Daniel W. Russell in 1996 and the Locus of Control Scale Indian Adaptation of Levenson Scale (Vohra, 1992). For the present research mean, standard deviation, and t-test: two samples assuming unequal variance were used to do the statistical analysis.

In the present research, the findings came out that there was a significant difference between powerful others, the power factor of locus of control was much higher in young adults belonging to nuclear families as compared to young adults belonging to joint families. There was no significant difference between chance control (external factors) and young adults in nuclear and joint families and there was no significant difference between individual control (internal factors) and young adults belonging to nuclear and joint families. The findings also show that there was no significant difference between young adults belonging to nuclear and joint families and loneliness. It also showed that young adults belonging to nuclear families have more external locus of control than young adults in joint families whereas there was no difference in young adults belonging to joint families in internal locus of control.

The configuration of authority, strength, and position as well as relationships, is referred to as family structure. The traditional family is made up of members from various generations who lived together. The nuclear family is the one in which the whole community consists of a male, his wife, and their kids.

When young adults begin to travel outside their immediate family to groups and colleges outside of their neighbourhood, they may face rejection from their peers. They are vulnerable to loneliness when confronted with such circumstances.

Loneliness is considered to be a universal phenomenon by every individual who has experienced it from time to time. It is the distress that occurs when one’s social relationships are perceived as being less satisfying than what is desired (Peplau & Perlman, 1982).

According to the results, there is no substantial difference between young adults from joint families and nuclear families and their level of loneliness. A similar study done by T. Matthews et. al (2016) studied Social isolation, loneliness, and depression in young adulthood: a behavioral genetic analysis concluded that Socially isolated young adults do not necessarily experience loneliness. However, those who are lonely are often depressed, partly because the same genes influence loneliness and depression.

Individual variations in the ability to adapt to various situations in life can be explained using the locus of control, a psychological concept. The locus of control is a measure of how people think they can control their lives and where they get that control. It is the perceived source of influence over the behavior.

The analysis showed that there is a significant difference between the powerful factor of locus of control among young adults belonging to nuclear families and joint families. Young adults belonging to nuclear families tend to have more external locus of control that is powerful others factor of locus of control when compared to young adults of joint families. Similarly, Muhammad Shoab, et.al. (2013) studied the “Role of Locus of Control in Marital Adjustment among School Teachers: A Study of Working Women in Gujarat-Pakistan”. And the results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between internal and external locus of control and marital adjustments. It also revealed that respondents from nuclear family system showed higher difference in locus of control and marital adjustment as compared to those who were from joint family system.

The analysis of the data also showed that there is no significant difference among young adults belonging to nuclear and joint families on the individual factor and chance control factor of locus of control. Similarly, Jayesh L. Gavit (2017) did a research on “Locus of Control, Insecurity, Lifestyle and Psychological Adjustment: A Comparative Study of Joint and Nuclear Family of College Students”. Results showed that there was no significant difference between joint and nuclear family of college students with reference to locus of control, insecurity, and psychological adjustments.

Young Adults in nuclear families have a greater external locus of control than young adults in joint/extended families, according to the results. This suggests that young adults believe that powerful others have greater influence over their results chance, destiny, and so on. According to studies by Ghuman, and Shoab (2013), respondents from nuclear families have a greater gap in the locus of control than respondents from joint families.

IX. CONCLUSION

The study did with the aim of investigating the level of loneliness and type of locus of control among young adults belonging to nuclear families and joint families and found out that there was no difference in the level of loneliness among adults belonging to joint families and nuclear families. It also indicated that the Powerful Others factor of locus of control (external factors) was high in young adults belonging to nuclear families when compared to young adults belonging to joint families. And it also concluded that there was no significant difference between internal locus of control and chance factor of locus of control among young adults belonging to joint families and nuclear families.

REFERENCES

- [1] Almajali, H. K. (2012). The Relationship of Family Upbringing Style with Locus Of Control Of Preparatory School Learners In Jordan. *European Scientific Journal, ESJ*, 8(13). <https://ejournal.org/index.php/esj/article/view/201>
- [2] Ayla Khan, Kanwal Shahbaz (2018) Influence of Family Structure on Social and Emotional Loneliness among Elders. *International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research* 6(2), 2018, pp. 27-35. ISSN 2348-2990
- [3] Chiao, C., Chen, Y., & Yi, C. A. (2019). Loneliness in young adulthood: It's intersecting forms and its association with psychological well-being and family characteristics in Northern Taiwan. *PLOS ONE*, 14(5), e0217777. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0217777>
- [4] Diehl, K., Jansen, C. H., Ishchanova, K., & Hilger-Kolb, J. (2018). Loneliness at Universities: Determinants of Emotional and Social Loneliness among Students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(9), 1865. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15091865>
- [5] Ghumman, A., Ghumman, S., & Shoaib, M. (2013). Role of Locus Control in Marital Adjustment among School Teachers: A Study of Working Women in Gujrat-Pakistan. *World Applied Science Journal*.
- [6] Holmqvist, S., & Östlund, J. (2019). The Experience of Loneliness In Young Adulthood: A Cross-Cultural Study (Dissertation). Retrieved from <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:umu:diva-167493>
- [7] Jain, M., & Singh, S. (2015). Locus of control and its relationship with mental health and adjustment among adolescent females. *Journal of Mental Health and Human Behaviour*, 20(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0971-8990.164803>
- [8] Javeed, Q. (2014) Relative Effect of Nuclear Family and Joint Family upon Emotional Intelligence and Loneliness. *Golden research thoughts*, 3(9): 1-4.
- [9] K, A., & S, K. (2018). Levels of Loneliness and Family Structure among Geriatrics. *Journal of Forensic Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2475-319x.1000135>
- [10] Kaura, N., & Sharma, R. (2015). Loneliness and Locus of Control among Adolescents Belonging To Nuclear and Joint Families. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.25215/0301.080>
- [11] L Gavit, J. (2019). Locus of Control, Insecurity, Lifestyle and Psychological Adjustment: A Comparative Study of Joint and Nuclear Family of College Students. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 4(5).
- [12] Lailun Nahar (2020). Effect of Family Type And Gender On Locus Of Control And Marital Adjustment Of Urban People November *Journal of Life and Earth Science* 14:99-104
- [13] Lodhi, F.S., Rabbani, U., Khan, A.A. *et al.* Factors associated with quality of life among joint and nuclear families: a population-based study. *BMC Public Health* 21, 234 (2021)
- [14] Łubianka, B., Filipiak, S., & Mariańczyk, K. (2020). Developmental Changes in the Locus of Control in Students Attending Integrated and Non-integrated Classes during Early Adolescence in Poland. *Behavioral Sciences*, 10(4), 74. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs10040074>
- [15] Matthews, T., Danese, A., Wertz, J., Odgers, C., Ambler, A. P., Moffitt, T. E., & Arseneault, L. (2016). Social isolation, loneliness and depression in young adulthood: a behavioural genetic analysis. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00127-016-1178-7>

- [16] Nidhi Mathur & Rajshree Vaishnav, 2017. "Intelligence And Social Adjustment of Joint And Nuclear Family Children Studying At High School Level," Working Papers 2017-24-01, Voice of Research. Rehman, R., & Singh, H. (2015). Family Type and Adjustment Level of Adolescents: A Study. *Journal of International Dental and Medical Research*; 1(6):22-25.
- [17] Nikhat, K. (2017). The Effect of Perceived Loneliness on Achievement Motivation Self Esteem and Locus of Control Among Adolescents. *University*. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/handle/10603/189023>
- [18] Ponzetti, J. J. (1990). Loneliness among College Students. *Family Relations*, 39(3), 336. <https://doi.org/10.2307/58488>
- [19] Puri, A. (2018, October 23). *Development of Loneliness Scale*. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328449451_Development_of_Loneliness_Scale
- [20] Rotter, Julian B. (1954). Social learning and clinical psychology. *New York: Prentice - Hall*, 1954.
- [21] Russell, D. W. (1996). UCLA Loneliness Scale (Version 3): Reliability, Validity, and Factor Structure. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 66(1), 20–40. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa6601_2
- [22] Selvaraj, A., & Gnanadevan, R. (2012). A Study on Loneliness of Normal School Students Studying Higher Secondary. *Golden Research Thoughts*, 2(3): 1-4.
- [23] Shinde, G., & Bhoi, R, M. (2014). Comparative Study of Social Adjustment Based on Family Type. *Scholarly Research journal for interdisciplinary studies, II (XY)*: 2561-2580.
- [24] Strate, Mary Margaret, "A study of the relationships of parents' locus of control and child-rearing attitudes to children's locus of control" (1987). *Dissertations, Theses, and Masters Projects*. William & Mary. Paper 1539618376. <https://dx.doi.org/doi:10.25774/w4-bbdb-0a20>
- [25] Usoroh, C. I., Akpan, I. D., Amadi, N. B., & Ezenwa, H. C. (2014). A Comparative Study of the Effect of Family Types on Social Adjustment of Adolescent in Aba, Abia State. *Civil and Environmental Research*, 6(8), 147–151. <https://iiste.org/Journals/index.php/CER/article/download/14705/15061>